

A Comparison of the Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools: The Reviewed Literature

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Abstract

this study was conducted to review the literature by comparing the job satisfaction of teachers in public and private secondary schools. The study particularly sought to compare the working conditions and the financial satisfaction of teachers in public secondary schools and those in private secondary schools in order to come up with some recommendations which could enhance the quality of education in secondary schools and teacher job satisfaction. The study established that teachers in private secondary schools that offer attractive salaries and adequate teaching and learning resources experience high levels of job satisfaction than those in public secondary schools where they do not receive good salaries and teaching resources. The secondary school teachers in public schools have secured jobs and salaries, therefore, they are likely to experience high levels of job satisfaction than those in private secondary schools. As such, the findings show that teacher job satisfaction in both public and private secondary schools varies depending on the conditions of work that those teachers are subjected to. The study therefore recommends that, public secondary schools should be provided with adequate teaching and learning resources. Moreover, the infrastructure of both public and private secondary schools should be improved and well maintained. The teacher salaries should be continuously reviewed and upgraded.

Key words: Job satisfaction; Public and Private secondary schools; Working conditions.

Introduction

Job satisfaction plays a crucial role towards the employees' commitment at work and the productivity of an organization (Baluyos, Rivera & Baluyos, 2019). International research shows that the level at which secondary school teachers are satisfied with their job and work conditions is likely to affect their efficiency at work, their approach to teaching, their relations with each other and students as well as learner academic performance (Haq & Hasnain, 2014). Teacher job satisfaction therefore has been indicated to influence the academic performance of learners and the school improvement cannot be achieved if teachers experience high levels of job dissatisfaction (Baluyos et al., 2019). As a result, it is pertinent for schools, both private and public to seriously consider how to improve teacher job satisfaction in order to produce high-quality learner performance (Mehta, 2012).

Lalita (2013) indicated that the job satisfaction of employees varies depending on the conditions of their workplace and their financial benefits. As such, when people are satisfied with their job, they are likely to be committed to their work and produce better organizational results (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011). This is because their satisfaction and dissatisfaction depend on the job and their expectation from the job (Lalita, 2013).

According to Suki and Suki (2011), the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers in either private or public schools determines their well-being and the academic performance of learners. Research shows that the level of teacher satisfaction is affected by both the intrinsic and extrinsic factors of motivation (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011). As indicated by Haq and Hasnain (2014), some of these factors include: attractive salaries, promotion, satisfactory working environments, adequate teaching and learning resources and other monetary incentives. Akhtah, Hashmi and Naqvi (2010) pointed out that the financial rewards, supervision, recognition and the working conditions were some of the factors which contributed hugely in the job satisfaction of teachers. As a result, the level of job satisfaction in teachers may positively or negatively contribute to learner academic performance. According to Dar (2014), job dissatisfaction is unpleasant and even harmful to any organization's success if not looked into with much consideration. Therefore, as noted by Dar (2014), when secondary school

teachers are not satisfied with their job, this might affect how they assist their learners and could impact on the overall performance of the school.

Jahan and Ahmed (2018) highlighted that satisfied and motivated teachers influence learners to learn through their unwavering commitment and efficiency. However, dissatisfied teachers may not be committed or productive at work and could not do their best to improve the school performance (Jahan & Ahmed, 2018). It is therefore significant to note that job satisfaction is related to teacher commitment towards improving the school performance. This study sought to compare the reviewed literature on the job satisfaction of teachers in public and private secondary schools in order to inform the recommendations geared towards improving the quality of education in both public and private sectors of education.

Objectives of the study

1. To compare the working conditions of teachers in public and private secondary schools.
2. To determine the financial satisfaction of teachers in public and private secondary schools.

Literature Review

The working conditions of teachers in public and private secondary schools

Both public and private secondary schools need highly motivated teachers to be able to achieve their organizational goals of providing quality education (Sonmeze & Eryama, 2008). Literature shows that for teachers to be satisfied with their job, they need to be happy with their working conditions and remuneration (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2007). It is significant for teachers as indicated by Msuya (2014) to be provided with satisfactory working conditions in order to enhance their job satisfaction levels, retain them in the job and also improve their job performance. Deconzo and Robins (1998) pointed out that teacher job satisfaction in both public and private secondary schools is likely to be affected by their working conditions.

In a study conducted by Shabbir (2014) on the job satisfaction status of public school teachers in Pakistan, the findings revealed that teachers were generally satisfied with supervision, salaries and promotion but not satisfied with the working conditions and the work itself. Nevertheless, the study also showed that the teachers in private secondary schools were not satisfied with their salaries and promotion but highly satisfied with their working conditions (Shabbir, 2014). The research revealed that the school infrastructure, particularly classrooms for the private secondary schools were satisfactory when compared to those in public secondary schools which were dilapidated and had poor ventilation (Shabbir, 2014).

In a similar study conducted by the National Centre for Education Statistics NCES (2009) entitled "What American Teachers Say about Teaching in Public and Private schools," two major aspects were reported. The first one was that, the private school teachers were found to be more satisfied than their public schools counterparts when it came to classroom conditions and the school climate. Secondly, while the teachers in public schools had challenges with heavy workloads and congested classrooms, private schools had manageable workloads and classes, better working conditions and stronger staff network. These findings implied that teachers in private secondary schools experienced high levels of job satisfaction than the teachers teaching in public secondary schools (NCES, 2009).

Lalita's (2013) study on a comparative analysis of job satisfaction among teachers of private and government schools concluded that, both private and government secondary school teachers showed low job satisfaction levels with their school working conditions. Moreover, a study which was done in three government secondary schools and three private secondary schools in Malaysia showed that teachers in government schools were significantly satisfied with their job, particularly with their working environment than those in private schools (Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016). The study results indicated that it is necessary for private secondary schools to

provide teachers with conducive working environments in order to improve their job satisfaction level (Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016).

A study conducted by Msuya (2014) found that secondary school teachers in the public schools in Tanzania were not satisfied with their working conditions. Their dissatisfaction was revealed by the low Standard Deviation of 1.02 and the Mean score of 2.8 which were obtained from the questionnaire results. In the study, the teachers complained of congested classrooms with broken doors, windows and with poor ventilation. However, Khalid (2012) found that teachers in private secondary schools in Pakistan were more satisfied with the availability of sufficient resources, well-resourced libraries and laboratories than their counterparts in public secondary schools.

In a comparative analysis of job satisfaction levels and motivation among teachers in government and private secondary schools in Harare, Zimbabwe, Nhuta and Nhuta (2017) discovered that the secondary school teachers in private schools were more satisfied ($M=11.456$, $SD=2.429$) with their working conditions than their government secondary schools counterparts ($M=10.091$, $SD=3.027$). The study stated that since private secondary schools enroll children from wealthy and knowledgeable families, they ensure that the schools are well resourced so that they retain those children in their schools. For this reason, according to Kumari, Joshi and Pandey (2014), the more the private secondary schools uphold the integrity of their schools through improved performance, the more children they enroll each year. However, Liu and Ramsey (2008) found that teachers in government secondary schools were least satisfied with their job and their working conditions in particular. This resulted in high teacher attrition or turnover whereby many of them left teaching for greener pastures. Nhuta and Nhuta's (2017) study showed that teachers in private secondary schools enjoy being given the responsibilities and recognition for their positive contributions in the schools, thus, further enhancing their job satisfaction levels.

The findings presented by the Council for American Private Education report (2014) revealed that many teachers in private secondary schools (90%) were provided with adequate teaching and learning materials for effective teaching and learning. Furthermore, the report showed that both teachers and learners in some private secondary schools had sufficient access to computers, printers, internet connections, core textbooks, tables and chairs and this made teaching and learning enjoyable (Council for American Private Education report, 2014). However, the report showed that 79% of public secondary school teachers had limited teaching and learning resources and this affected the teaching process in general. In the report, the public secondary school teachers highlighted that students shared a few computers, textbooks and even chairs. This increased the teachers' dissatisfaction level which was also heightened by the unpleasant school working conditions (Muga, Onyango & Jackline, 2017). The study concluded that teachers in private secondary schools have high levels of teacher job dissatisfaction when it came to the provision of the necessary teaching and learning resources as compared to their public secondary schools counterparts (Council for American Private Education report, 2014; Muga et al, 2017).

The financial satisfaction of teachers in public and private secondary schools

The situation of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction of the employees as pointed out by Spector (1997) depends on how they are remunerated. It is therefore the responsibility of an institution to provide proper financial rewards to its employees in order to motivate them and improve their work performance. For that reason, Spector (1997) argued that there is need for both the public and private secondary school teachers to be financially satisfied for their practice in teaching to be improved. The most notable aspect of job satisfaction in employees is salary (Kumari et al., 2014). A study by Dole and Schroeder (2001) found that 112 out of 192 public secondary school teachers in the United States of America (21.17%) said they would prefer private schools if they had the opportunity to transfer. The respondents mentioned that the salary factor was the major

reason of their preference of private schools (Dole & Schroeder, 2001). Research therefore shows that salary plays a pivotal role in every employee's life, and teachers inclusive (Rahman, Rahman & Ali, 2015).

A study by Nhuta and Nhuta (2017) in Zimbabwe found that the teachers in private secondary schools were more satisfied with their income ($M=17.087$, $SD=5.778$) than the teachers in government secondary schools ($M=5.778$, $SD=3.670$). The results of their study revealed that teachers in private secondary schools received more salaries and other financial benefits than those in public secondary schools. Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2007) as a result, highlighted that the salary factor lowers teacher job satisfaction in public secondary schools.

On the contrary, a study conducted by Raghavaya and Susmitha (2018) on the job satisfaction in public and private secondary school teachers with reference to Vasakhapatnam City revealed that there is a significant difference in the job satisfaction levels of public and private secondary school teachers with regard to their salaries. The study concluded that the satisfaction level of public secondary school teachers is greater than that of private secondary school teachers (Raghavaya & Susmitha, 2018). The findings of the study highlighted that not all private secondary schools offer attractive salaries to their teachers. As such, those teachers in private secondary schools which pay them well could have high levels of job satisfaction, while those whose private secondary schools pay little are likely to experience low job satisfaction levels (Raghavaya & Susmitha, 2018).

Ahmed's (2014) study revealed that the mostly cited factor of job dissatisfaction among both public and private secondary school teachers was poor remuneration or salary. The teachers in both types of secondary schools indicated that they were not satisfied with their finances. However, it was evident that apart from a very few urban private secondary schools, public secondary school teachers get a comparatively higher salary on regular basis. Furthermore, public secondary school teachers were also reported to be having a financially protected future in terms of retirement benefits than their private secondary schools counterparts (Ahmed, 2014).

Moreover, unlike teachers in private secondary schools who are not assured of their continual salary and job security, the job security factor makes public secondary school teachers' job satisfaction level higher than private secondary school teachers (Msuya, 2014). Despite that some of the private secondary school teachers earn more than public school teachers, they do not have a stable job security, thus this might affect their job satisfaction (Msuya, 2014). The teachers in public secondary schools are therefore assured of their job security as they have permanent contracts when compared to private secondary school teachers (Sönmeze & Eryama, 2008).

Conclusions

Teacher job satisfaction is crucial for job performance, teacher well being and organizational success. Both teachers in private and public secondary schools need to be satisfied with their job for them to perform better. The level of job satisfaction in both private and public secondary schools depends on their working conditions and how they are rewarded financially. Most of the reviewed literature shows that teachers in the private secondary schools are more satisfied with their working conditions than the teachers in public secondary schools. Research has further established that private secondary schools are well resourced with adequate textbooks, computers, internet connections and furniture in order to lure more parents to enroll their children in their schools. Hence, this enhances the job satisfaction of teachers in private secondary schools. Despite that some teachers in other private secondary schools earn lower salaries than those in public secondary schools, they are more satisfied with their job than their public secondary schools counterparts as they feel more recognized and supported.

Recommendations

- The public secondary schools should be provided with adequate teaching and learning resources such as textbooks, tables, chairs and computers and internet connectivity for all learners to use.
- The infrastructure of both public and private secondary schools should be improved and well maintained.
- The salaries of both public and private secondary school teachers should be continuously reviewed and improved in order to enhance teacher job satisfaction.

Future research

- To conduct a study on the provision of teaching and learning resources in public and private secondary schools in Botswana.
- To carry out a research on a comparative analysis of teacher job satisfaction and learner performance of public and private secondary schools.
- To carry out a research on job satisfaction, teacher resilience and efficacy in public secondary schools in Botswana.

References

- i. Akhtah, S. N., Hashmi, M. A., & Naqvi, S. H. (2010). *A comparative study of job satisfaction in public and private school teachers at secondary level. Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 2(2), 4222- 4228.
- ii. Ahmed, O. (2014). *Job Satisfaction of Teachers at Private and Public Secondary Schools. Bangladesh Journal of Psychology*, 20(1), 31-41.
- iii. Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). *Teachers' job satisfaction and work performance. Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1), 206 - 221.
- iv. Deconzo, D.A., & Robins, S. P. (1998). *Personnel/Human Resource Management, 3rd Ed, Hall of India Private Limited New Delhi - Asoka Ghosh, Prentice.*
- v. Dole, C., & Schroeder, R.G. (2001). *The impact of various factors on the personality, job satisfaction and turnover intentions of professional accountants. Managerial Auditing Journal*, 16(4), 235–236.
- vi. Ghavifekr, S., & Pillai, N. S. (2016). *The relationship between School's organizational climate and Teachers' job satisfaction: Malaysian Experience. Asia Pacific Education Review*, 17(1), 87-106.
- vii. Jahan, M., & Ahmed, M. (2018). *Teachers' job satisfaction: A study in secondary schools in Bangladesh. Journal of Contemporary Teacher Education*, 2(1), 71-91.
- viii. Kumari, G., Joshi, G. & Pandey, K. M. (2014) *Analysis of factors affecting job satisfaction of the employees in public and private sector. International Journal of Trends in Economics Management and Technology*, 3(1), 1-19.
- ix. Lalita, T. R. (2013). *A comparative analysis of Job satisfaction among teachers of private and government schools concluded that both private and government school teachers. International Journal of Social Science and Interdisciplinary Research*, 2(9), 151-157.
- x. Mehta, D. S. (2012). *Job satisfaction among teachers. International Journal of Research in Commerce IT & Management*, 2(4), 77- 83.
- xi. Muga, O. P., Onyango, A. G. & Jackline, N. (2017) *Levels of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Siaya, Kisumu and Kajiado Counties, Kenya. European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(8), 684 -702.
- xii. Msuya, O. W. (2014). *Exploring levels of job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools in Tanzania. International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 8(2), 9 -16.
- xiii. Nhuta, S., & Nhuta, P. (2017). *Job satisfaction levels and motivation among teachers: A comparative analysis of teachers in government and private schools. Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 4(1), 36- 60.
- xiv. Rahman, W., Rahman, H., & Ali, F. (2015). *Interrelationships of employee development, Organisational commitment, job satisfaction and their impact on turnover intentions. City University Research Journal*, 5(2), 301-314.

- xv. Raghavaya, V., & Susmitha, K. (2018). *A study of job satisfaction in public and private school teachers with reference to Vasakhapatnam City. International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 7(4), 463- 471.
- xvi. Shabbir, M. (2014). *The job satisfaction status of public school teachers: A case of Pakistan Administrative Kashmir. European Journal of Educational Sciences*, 1(4), 56 – 70.
- xvii. Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2011). *Teacher job satisfaction and motivation to leave the teaching profession: Relations with school context, feeling of belonging, and emotional exhaustion. Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27(6), 1029–1038.
- xviii. Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2007). *Dimensions of teacher self-efficacy and relations with strain factors, perceived collective teacher efficacy, and teacher burnout. Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(1), 611-625.
- xix. Sonmeze, M., & Eryama, M. Y. (2008). *A comparative analysis of job satisfaction levels of public and private school teachers. Journal of Theory and Practice in Education*, 4(2), 189-212
- xx. Spector, P. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, Assessment, causes and consequences*, London: Sage publications.
- xxi. Suki, N., & Suki, N. (2011). *Job satisfaction and Organisational Commitment: The effect of Gender. International Journal of Psychology Research*, 6(5), 1-15.